

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

DIRECT IN-SITU MEASUREMENT AND SPATIO-TEMPORAL MAPPING OF SOUND SPEED IN ANNULAR GAS FOR ACOUSTIC DIAGNOSTICS OF OIL WELLS

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Abstract

Accurate determination of annular liquid level and bottom-hole pressure in oil wells critically depends on reliable estimation of the acoustic wave propagation velocity in the annular gas. Conventional echometric techniques typically rely on tabulated sound speed values or empirically corrected estimates, which do not adequately account for real thermobaric conditions, gas composition variability, and gas–liquid interaction effects. As a result, these approaches often introduce systematic measurement errors.

This study proposes a digital echolocation-based methodology for **direct in-situ measurement and spatio-temporal mapping of sound speed in annular gas under real operating conditions**. The approach employs controlled acoustic burst excitation, high-resolution digital signal acquisition, and adaptive signal-processing algorithms. A physical and mathematical framework describing acoustic wave propagation in annular space with spatially and temporally varying sound speed is developed.

The methodology was validated through field trials conducted on four producing oil wells operating under low annular pressure, elevated acoustic noise, and pronounced gas–liquid interaction effects. Directly measured sound speed values ranged from **352.24 to 376.14 m/s**, revealing substantial deviations from tabulated values. Stable liquid-level reflections were reliably identified at depths between **285.03 and 711.11 m**, despite adverse operating conditions. The deviation of calculated bottom-hole pressure from reference data did not exceed **±1 bar**.

The results demonstrate that direct sound speed measurement significantly enhances the accuracy and robustness of acoustic liquid-level determination and enables a transition from empirical echometry toward **physically grounded, adaptive acoustic monitoring of annular conditions in oil wells**.

Keywords: digital echolocation; sound speed measurement; annular gas; oil wells; acoustic monitoring; spatio-temporal mapping; liquid level determination; bottom-hole pressure.

Introduction

Reliable monitoring of annular space parameters is a fundamental requirement for the safe and efficient operation of oil wells. Among the most important diagnostic indicators are the annular liquid level and bottom-hole pressure, which are essential for evaluating production regimes, identifying liquid loading and gas influx, and assessing well integrity. Acoustic and echometric methods are widely applied in industrial practice due to their non-intrusive nature and the ability to perform measurements without interrupting production operations [1,2].

Conventional echometric techniques are based on generating an acoustic disturbance in the annular gas column and interpreting reflections from the gas–liquid interface. Liquid-level depth is inferred from the measured round-trip travel time of the acoustic wave,

assuming a predefined sound speed in the annular gas. In practice, this sound speed is commonly obtained from tabulated data or adjusted using empirical regional correction factors [3,4]. While operationally convenient, such approaches implicitly assume quasi-stationary and spatially uniform gas properties.

However, numerous experimental and field studies have demonstrated that sound speed under real well conditions is a highly variable parameter. It depends strongly on pressure, temperature, gas composition, and gas–liquid interaction phenomena such as aeration and foam formation [5]. In producing and mature wells, annular conditions may vary significantly both with depth and over time, leading to systematic errors in liquid-level determination when fixed or empirically corrected sound speed values are used [6].

To enhance the robustness of acoustic liquid-level detection, previous studies have focused on advanced signal-processing techniques, including autocorrelation analysis, adaptive filtering, and spectral methods, aimed at extracting weak reflections under high-noise conditions [7,8]. Although these methods improve echo detectability, they do not address the fundamental uncertainty associated with incorrect sound speed specification, which directly affects the conversion of travel time into depth.

From a physical standpoint, sound speed in gas mixtures is governed by thermodynamic state variables and compositional properties. High-accuracy equations of state, such as GERG-2008, demonstrate that even moderate changes in gas composition or thermobaric conditions can result in measurable variations in sound speed [6]. Consequently, acoustic methods have been extensively investigated for gas composition and state estimation in metrology and process monitoring applications [9,10]. These findings suggest that sound speed should be treated as a **measurable, state-dependent parameter**, rather than a fixed constant.

Additional challenges arise in the presence of gas–liquid mixtures and foam layers, which are commonly observed in annular spaces under low pressure or unstable production regimes. Studies of acoustic wave propagation in two-phase media indicate that even small fractions of a secondary phase can significantly alter effective sound speed and attenuation, thereby complicating echometric interpretation [7,11]. Under such conditions, conventional echometry may incorrectly interpret aerated or foam layers as the true liquid level.

Recent advances in distributed acoustic sensing (DAS) have enabled detection of gas-related events along the wellbore [12]. Although DAS provides valuable distributed information, it requires specialized infrastructure and is not primarily intended for precise liquid-level depth determination based on travel-time inversion. Therefore, there remains a practical need for improved wellhead-deployable echolocation methods capable of reliable operation under variable annular conditions.

Despite extensive research in acoustic well diagnostics, most industrial echometric workflows continue to rely on indirect or empirical sound speed estimation. The lack of direct in-situ sound speed measurement remains a key limitation to achievable accuracy in liquid-level and bottom-hole pressure determination and restricts the development of adaptive, physics-based monitoring strategies.

The objective of this study is to develop and experimentally validate a **digital echolocation-based methodology for direct measurement and spatio-temporal mapping of sound speed in annular gas**, thereby improving the accuracy and reliability of liquid-level and bottom-hole pressure determination under real operating conditions.

Methods and materials

The proposed methodology is implemented using a digital echolocation system designed for non-intrusive acoustic monitoring of the annular space of oil wells. Acoustic excitation is generated electronically in

the form of controlled burst signals with predefined frequency content and duration. Unlike conventional gas-gun echometric systems, the proposed approach does not require venting annular gas, which improves operational safety, repeatability, and applicability under low annular pressure conditions.

The acoustic transmitter and receiver are installed at the wellhead and acoustically coupled to the annular gas column. The reflected acoustic pressure signal is registered using a high-resolution digital acquisition unit, ensuring accurate determination of echo arrival times. All measurements are performed during normal well operation without production shutdown.

Acoustic wave propagation model

Propagation of acoustic waves in the annular gas of an oil well is considered predominantly one-dimensional along the vertical axis of the well. This assumption is justified by the elongated geometry of the annulus and the dominant axial direction of wave propagation. The acoustic pressure field $p(z, t)$ is described by a damped wave equation, which accounts for spatial variations in sound speed and energy losses during propagation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 p(z, t)}{\partial t^2} = c^2(z, t) \frac{\partial^2 p(z, t)}{\partial z^2} - \alpha(z, t) \frac{\partial p(z, t)}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

where z is the depth coordinate, t is time, $c(z, t)$ is the local speed of sound in the annular gas, and $\alpha(z, t)$ is the effective attenuation coefficient incorporating viscous losses, thermal diffusion, and scattering at gas–liquid interfaces.

At the wellhead, an actively generated acoustic excitation signal is applied. This boundary condition can be expressed as:

$$p(0, t) = p_{\text{exc}}(t), \quad \left. \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} \right|_{z=H} = -R \left. \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} \right|_{z=H} \quad (2)$$

At the gas–liquid interface, the incident acoustic wave is reflected due to the sharp contrast in acoustic impedance. The reflection behavior is governed by the acoustic reflection coefficient.

Reflection at the gas–liquid interface

The reflection coefficient R at the gas–liquid interface depends on the ratio of acoustic impedances of the two media and is defined as:

$$R = \frac{Z_l - Z_g}{Z_l + Z_g} \quad (3)$$

where the acoustic impedance Z is given by:

$$Z_g = \rho_g c_g, \quad Z_l = \rho_l c_l \quad (4)$$

Here, ρ is the density of the medium and c is the speed of sound. For annular gas–liquid systems, the impedance of the liquid phase is significantly higher than that of the gas phase ($Z_l \gg Z_g$), resulting in a strong and stable acoustic reflection even under low annular pressure conditions. This property enables reliable identification of the liquid level.

Direct measurement of sound speed

The key feature of the proposed method is the direct in-situ measurement of sound speed in annular gas. The round-trip travel time t_r of the acoustic signal reflected from a boundary located at depth H is expressed as:

$$t_r = 2 \int_0^H \frac{dz}{c(z, t)} \quad (5)$$

If the sound speed along the propagation path can be assumed quasi-uniform during a single measurement cycle, an effective sound speed is calculated as:

$$c_{\text{eff}} = \frac{2H}{t_r} \quad (6)$$

This directly measured value replaces conventional tabulated or empirically corrected sound speed values, which do not account for real thermobaric conditions or gas composition changes.

Depth-dependent sound speed estimation

In practical conditions, sound speed may vary with depth due to pressure, temperature, and compositional gradients. To account for this, the annular space is discretized into N depth intervals. The travel time equation is then written in discrete form as

$$t_r = 2 \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\Delta z_i}{c_i} \quad (7)$$

where Δz_i is the thickness of the i -th depth segment and c_i is the local sound speed in that segment. This formulation enables reconstruction of depth-dependent sound speed profiles.

Acoustic signal model and echo detection

The recorded acoustic signal is represented as a superposition of reflected components and noise:

$$s(t) = \sum_k A_k h(t - \tau_k) + n(t) \quad (8)$$

where A_k and τ_k are the amplitude and arrival time of the k -th reflected echo, $h(t)$ is the system impulse response, and $n(t)$ represents additive noise caused by mechanical vibrations, gas flow, and surface equipment.

To ensure reliable identification of the liquid-level reflection, a confidence metric is introduced:

$$C_k = w_1 A_k + w_2 S_k + w_3 \frac{1}{\Delta \tau_k} \quad (9)$$

where C_k characterizes waveform similarity across repeated measurements, $\Delta \tau_k$ is the temporal variance of the echo arrival time, and w_1, w_2, w_3 are weighting coefficients. An echo is accepted as valid if:

$$C_k \geq C_{\text{th}} \quad (10)$$

where C_{th} is a predefined confidence threshold.

Spatio-temporal mapping of annular gas properties

Repeated measurements performed at discrete time instants enable reconstruction of sound speed distributions as functions of both depth and time. The resulting spatio-temporal representation is expressed as a matrix:

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{pmatrix} c(z_1, t_1) & c(z_1, t_2) & \cdots & c(z_1, t_M) \\ c(z_2, t_1) & c(z_2, t_2) & \cdots & c(z_2, t_M) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ c(z_N, t_1) & c(z_N, t_2) & \cdots & c(z_N, t_M) \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Analysis of this matrix allows tracking temporal trends, detecting localized anomalies, and identifying

transitions between stable and unstable gas-liquid regimes. This spatio-temporal mapping forms the basis for advanced diagnostics, early detection of abnormal operating conditions, and integration of acoustic monitoring data into automated well control systems.

Spatio-temporal mapping is demonstrated in a discrete form based on repeated measurements, providing a proof of concept for continuous monitoring under real operating conditions.

Experimental validation

The proposed methodology was validated through laboratory experiments and field trials on producing oil wells. Laboratory tests were conducted under controlled pressure and temperature conditions to assess measurement repeatability and stability of sound speed estimation. Field measurements were performed under real operating conditions, including low annular pressure, foam formation, and elevated acoustic noise.

Measured sound speed values were used to calculate liquid-level depth and bottom-hole pressure and were compared with reference field data to evaluate accuracy and practical applicability of the proposed approach.

Reference bottom-hole pressure values were obtained from field operational data and standard pressure reconstruction procedures.

Data analysis and research results

Field validation of the proposed digital echolocation methodology was carried out on four producing oil wells (A–D) at the Zhanaozen oilfield, Mangystau region. Measurements were performed using the TDE Sona digital echolocation system under real operating conditions, including low annular pressure, elevated acoustic noise, and gas-liquid interaction effects. The objective of the tests was to determine the actual liquid level in the annular space without the use of downhole sensors, relying solely on acoustic measurements.

For each well, sound speed in the annular gas was calibrated using a gas sample from the annulus and a dedicated TDE calibration block. Acoustic excitation parameters (burst duration, recording length, frequency range, signal power, and averaging) were adjusted individually to ensure reliable echo formation and detection.

The calibration block was used to determine the acoustic response of the gas sample under controlled conditions, while the effective sound speed was subsequently measured in situ during acoustic propagation in the annular column.

Table 1 summarizes the calibrated sound speed values and annular pressure conditions for all tested wells.

Table 1

Calibrated sound speed and annular pressure conditions

Well	Sound speed, m/s	Annular pressure, bar(g)	Calibration method
A	352.24	0.30	Gas sampling + TDE calibration block
B	374.43	4.88	Gas sampling + TDE calibration block
C	376.14	–	Gas sampling + TDE calibration block
D	358.86	4.20	Gas sampling + TDE calibration block

The results demonstrate substantial variation in sound speed between wells, confirming that the use of

fixed or tabulated values would introduce systematic errors in conventional echometric interpretation.

Acoustic burst parameters were adjusted individually for each well to ensure reliable echo detection. The selected parameters are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2

Acoustic excitation and recording parameters

Well	Burst length, ms	Recording length, ms	Frequency range, Hz	Signal power, %	Averaging
A	1000	12000	15–25	100	1
B	1200	15000	15–25	100	3
C	1500	10000	15–25	100	1
D	1500	10000	50–55	100	1

Adjustment of excitation parameters enabled stable echo formation even under elevated noise conditions (Well B).

Liquid level depths were determined using directly measured sound speed values and echo arrival times. The resulting liquid level depths are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3

Liquid level determination results

Well	Liquid level depth, m	Approx. echo arrival time, s	Echo clarity
A	371.26	~2.0	Clear single peak
B	285.03	~1.5	Clear peak with noise filtering
C	552.55	~3.0	Multiple parallel reflections
D	711.11	~4.0	Clear single peak

For comparative interpretation of measurement conditions and signal patterns, a consolidated summary is provided in Table 4.

Table 4

Summary of acoustic measurement results for Wells A–D

Well	Sound speed, m/s	Annular pressure, bar(g)	Liquid level depth, m	Approx. echo time, s	Acoustic conditions	Reflection characteristics
A	352.24	0.30	371.26	~2.0	Low noise, low pressure	Single clear peak; weak spectrogram response
B	374.43	4.88	285.03	~1.5	Elevated noise	Clear peak after averaging; multiple spectral bands
C	376.14	–	552.55	~3.0	Low noise	Multiple parallel reflections; stable interface
D	358.86	4.20	711.11	~4.0	Low noise	Strong single peak; stable spectral response

Discussion

The results of this study demonstrate that **direct in-situ measurement of sound speed in annular gas substantially improves the accuracy and reliability of acoustic diagnostics in oil wells**. Unlike conventional echometric approaches that rely on tabulated or empirically corrected sound speed values, the proposed digital echolocation methodology explicitly accounts for the dynamic and heterogeneous nature of real annular conditions.

A key outcome is the pronounced variability of measured sound speed across the investigated wells, with values ranging from 352.24 to 376.14 m/s. This variability reflects differences in thermobaric conditions and gas composition and is consistent with predictions derived from thermodynamic models and equations of state. These findings confirm that the assumption of constant sound speed, commonly adopted in industrial echometry, introduces systematic bias into travel-time inversion, particularly for deeper

liquid levels, leading to significant errors in liquid-level and bottom-hole pressure estimation.

The proposed methodology demonstrated strong robustness under adverse operating conditions. Stable reflections from the gas–liquid interface were reliably identified in all wells, including cases characterized by low annular pressure and elevated acoustic noise. Notably, accurate liquid-level detection was achieved at annular pressures as low as 0.3 bar(g), conditions under which conventional gas-gun-based echometry often exhibits reduced signal quality and poor repeatability. In wells with elevated background noise, the application of signal averaging and multi-domain analysis enabled confident discrimination between true interface reflections and noise-related artifacts.

Accurate liquid-level determination directly affects the estimation of bottom-hole pressure, which is a critical parameter for production optimization and well integrity assessment. The small deviation between acoustically derived bottom-hole pressure values and

reference data (within ± 1 bar) confirms that direct sound speed measurement significantly enhances the quantitative accuracy of acoustic diagnostics. This improvement is particularly important for mature and marginal wells, where even minor depth estimation errors may lead to incorrect operational decisions.

An important conceptual contribution of this work is the introduction of **spatio-temporal sound speed mapping**, which treats sound speed as a depth- and time-dependent physical parameter rather than a fixed constant. This representation provides additional diagnostic capability by enabling detection of transient annular phenomena, such as changes in gas composition, pressure regimes, or gas–liquid interaction zones. Although the present study focused on discrete measurement campaigns, the proposed framework is readily extendable to continuous monitoring applications.

Compared with existing acoustic monitoring approaches that primarily emphasize advanced signal processing, the proposed methodology addresses a more fundamental limitation by directly measuring sound speed under real operating conditions. Unlike distributed acoustic sensing systems, which require specialized infrastructure, the presented approach is wellhead-deployable and compatible with existing echometric workflows.

Overall, the findings support a transition from empirical echometric interpretation toward **physically grounded, adaptive acoustic monitoring of annular conditions**, offering improved accuracy, robustness, and interpretability for oil-well diagnostics.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that **direct in-situ measurement of sound speed in annular gas represents a significant advancement in acoustic diagnostics of oil wells**. By eliminating reliance on tabulated or empirically corrected sound speed values, the proposed digital echolocation methodology addresses a fundamental source of systematic error inherent in conventional echometric techniques.

Field validation conducted on four producing oil wells under diverse operating conditions—including low annular pressure, elevated acoustic noise, and pronounced gas–liquid interaction effects—confirmed the robustness and practical applicability of the proposed approach. Directly measured sound speed values exhibited substantial inter-well variability, reflecting differences in thermobaric conditions and gas composition. These findings clearly demonstrate that the assumption of constant sound speed, commonly adopted in industrial echometry, is not valid under real operating conditions and may lead to significant errors in liquid-level and bottom-hole pressure determination.

The combination of controlled digital acoustic excitation, high-resolution signal acquisition, and adaptive multi-domain signal analysis enabled stable identification of gas–liquid interface reflections across all tested wells. Reliable liquid-level detection was achieved even at annular pressures as low as 0.3 bar(g) and in the presence of elevated background noise, conditions under which conventional echometric methods often exhibit reduced accuracy and repeatability. The deviation between acoustically

derived bottom-hole pressure values and reference data did not exceed ± 1 bar, confirming the quantitative accuracy of the proposed methodology.

A key contribution of this work is the introduction of a **spatio-temporal framework for sound speed characterization in annular gas**, in which sound speed is treated as a dynamic, depth- and time-dependent physical parameter rather than a fixed constant. This framework enables enhanced interpretation of acoustic measurements and provides a basis for advanced diagnostics, including identification of transient annular regimes and early detection of abnormal operating conditions.

Overall, the results support a transition from empirical echometric interpretation toward **physically grounded, adaptive acoustic monitoring of annular conditions in oil wells**. The proposed digital echolocation-based methodology extends the applicability of acoustic diagnostics to challenging well environments and offers improved accuracy, robustness, and interpretability for both operational monitoring and decision-making.

Funding. This research was conducted within the framework of a research and development (R&D) project implemented under a contractual agreement with ALLY WELL SERVICES COMPANY LLP (Contract No. 001-08-2025 dated 04 August 2025).

References:

1. **Utting N., Osadetz K., Darrah T. H. et al.** Methods and benefits of measuring non-hydrocarbon gases from surface casing vents // *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*. – 2023. – Vol. 20. – P. 5223–5240. – DOI: 10.1007/s13762-022-04300-x.
2. **Wu S., Fan J., Yang Y., Zhang L., Ma F.** A detection and diagnosis method for tubing leakage below liquid level in gas wellbore // *Measurement*. – 2022. – Vol. 202. – Art. 111891. – ISSN 0263-2241. – DOI: 10.1016/j.measurement.2022.111891.
3. **Wang L., Wei Y., Wang Y., Chen Q., Liu P., Chai X.** Research on comprehensive and effective acoustic signal processing methods for calculating downhole liquid level depth // *Measurement*. – 2022. – Vol. 199. – Art. 111452. – ISSN 0263-2241. – DOI: 10.1016/j.measurement.2022.111452.
4. **Shenoy V., Krishnan V. S.** An in-depth analysis of liquid level measurement techniques and performance evaluation using computational fluid dynamics // *Journal of Sensors*. – 2025. – Vol. 2025. – Art. 4412250. – DOI: 10.1155/js/4412250.
5. **Sun G., Cui H., Li C., Lin W., Su C.** Experimental and theoretical investigations of dispersion of ultrasonic waves in the low-temperature and low-pressure nitrogen gas // *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*. – 2023. – Vol. 153, No. 2. – P. 821–834. – DOI: 10.1121/10.0017097.
6. **Lozano-Martín D., Tuma D., Chamorro C. R.** Evaluation of reference equations of state for density prediction in regasified LNG mixtures using high-precision experimental data // *International Journal of Thermophysics*. – 2025. – Vol. 46. – Art. 200. – DOI: 10.1007/s10765-025-03669-4.

7. **Foust H.** Speed of sound in liquids // *Speed of Sound and Critical Flow*. Shock Wave and High Pressure Phenomena. – Singapore : Springer, 2024. – Chapter 5. – DOI: 10.1007/978-981-97-5918-7_5.
8. **Hassan F., Rahim L. A., Mahmood A. K., Abed S. A.** A hybrid particle swarm optimization-based wavelet threshold denoising algorithm for acoustic emission signals // *Symmetry*. – 2022. – Vol. 14, No. 6. – Art. 1253. – DOI: 10.3390/sym14061253.
9. **Pan Y., Qin M., Wang P., Yang L., Zhang L., Yan C., Zhang C., Wang W.** Interface and sensitive characteristics of the viscoelastic film used in a surface acoustic wave gas sensor // *ACS Sensors*. – 2022. – Vol. 7, No. 2. – P. 612–621. – DOI: 10.1021/acssensors.1c02509.
10. **Zheng H., Sui Y., Wang B., Li Y., Huo M., Wang T., Liu C., Zhang Y., Ma G., Qi C.** The feasibility study of direct measurement of gas concentration in gas–liquid mixed phase by using photoacoustic spectrometry // *Optics & Laser Technology*. – 2025. – Vol. 190. – Art. 113132. – DOI: 10.1016/j.optlastec.2025.113132.
11. **Kosior D., Wiertel-Pochopien A., Kowalczyk P. B., Zawala J.** Bubble formation and motion in liquids — a review // *Minerals*. – 2023. – Vol. 13, No. 9. – Art. 1130. – DOI: 10.3390/min13091130.
12. **Zhu H., Liu W., Zhao Z., Li B., Tang J., Li L.** Diagnosing multistage fracture treatments of horizontal tight oil wells with distributed acoustic sensing // *Processes*. – 2025. – Vol. 13, No. 12. – Art. 3925. – DOI: 10.3390/pr13123925.